

HALOGENATION. PART XVII. BROMINATION AND IODINATION OF DIPHENYL.

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Bromo and iodo derivatives of diphenyl have been obtained indirectly from benzidine and by the use of Ullmann's reaction (*Annalen*, 1904, 392, 57). Bromo derivatives have been obtained by direct bromination also (Scholl and Neovius, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 10). 4:4'-Diiiododiphenyl has been obtained by the action of sulphur and iodine in presence of nitric acid (Wilgerodt and Hilgenberg, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 3826).

We have studied the action of bromine and iodine on diphenyl in presence of (a) fuming nitric acid, (b) fuming sulphuric acid or a mixture of both, (c) sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid, and (d) a mixture of fuming nitric and nitrosulphonic acids. Under these conditions a smaller amount of bromine is required and even iodine acts directly. 4:4'-Dibromo- and 4:4'-diiiododiphenyl is obtained in good yield and 2:2'-dibromodiphenyl in small quantities as a bye-product.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4:4'-Dibromodiphenyl.—A solution of diphenyl (5 g.) in carbon tetrachloride (15 c. c.), bromine (3 c.c.) and sodium nitrite (5 g.) were heated on a water-bath with a reflux condenser and fuming sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) was added gradually to the mixture. The contents of the flask were heated for 3 hours and then allowed to stand overnight. The liquid portion was removed from the flask and washed free from acid and carbon tetrachloride distilled off. A residue was obtained (0.3 g.) which was found to be 2:2'-dibromodiphenyl, m.p. 81°.

The solid portion was washed free from acid and unused diphenyl was removed by washing with alcohol. It is crystallised from glacial acetic acid and is found to be 4:4'-dibromodiphenyl (6.2 g.), m.p. 164°.

4:4'-Diiiododiphenyl was obtained from diphenyl (5 g.) dissolved in acetic acid (15 c.c.), iodine (10 g.) and nitrosulphonic acid (5 c.c.), the last being added from the top of the condenser drop by drop and the whole heated for about 2 hours on a water-bath. After being washed, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid it melted at 202°, yield 6.2 g.